

SALT-TOLERANT AND PHOSPHATE-MOBILIZING PROPERTIES OF ACTINOMYCETES ISOLATED FROM SALINE SOILS

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Abstract. *The search and use of microorganisms that are resistant to high salt concentrations and capable of mobilizing poorly soluble forms of phosphorus is a promising direction in the development of microbial biopreparations to increase crop yields under stress conditions. In this work, the salt tolerance and phosphate-mobilizing activity of actinomycetes isolated from saline agrocenoses were studied. Isolates were found that showed growth at NaCl concentrations up to 7% and were capable of dissolving inorganic phosphates. The results confirm the potential of actinomycetes as a basis for developing microbial inoculants adapted to salt stress.*

Key words: *actinomycetes, saline soils, salt tolerance, phosphate mobilization, biopreparations, sustainable agriculture.*

Abstrakt. *Yuqori tuz kontsentratsiyasiga chidamli va fosforning qiyin eriydigan shakllarini o'simliklar tomonidan o'zlashtiriladigan shakllarga o'tkazish xususiyatiga ega mikroorganizmlarni izlash va ulardan foydalanish stressli sharoitlarda hosildorlikni oshirish uchun microbial biopreparatlarni ishlab chiqishning istiqbolli yo'nalishi hisoblanadi. Bu ishda sho'rlangan agrotsenozlardan ajratilgan aktinomitsetlarning tuzga chidamliligi va fosfat mobilizatsiyalash faolligi o'rganildi. NaCl kontsentratsiyasida 7% gacha o'sishni ko'rsatadigan va noorganik fosfatlarni eritish xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan izolyatlar aniqlandi. Olingan natijalar tuz stressiga moslashgan microbial inokulyantlarni ishlab chiqish uchun asos sifatida aktinomitsetlarning salohiyatini tasdiqlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aktinomitsetalar, sho'rlangan tuproqlar, tuzga chidamlilik, fosfat mobilizatsiyalash, biopreparatlar, barqaror qishloq xo'jaligi.*

Аннотация. *Поиск и использование микроорганизмов, обладающих устойчивостью к высоким концентрациям солей и способностью мобилизовать труднорастворимые формы фосфора, представляет собой перспективное направление в развитии микробных биопрепаратов для повышения урожайности в стрессовых условиях. В данной работе исследована солеустойчивость и фосфатмобилизирующая активность актиномицетов, выделенных из засоленных агроценозов. Выявлены изоляты, проявляющие рост при концентрации NaCl до 7% и способные растворять неорганические фосфаты. Полученные результаты подтверждают потенциал актиномицетов в качестве основы для разработки микробных инокулянтов, адаптированных к солевому стрессу.*

Ключевые слова: *актиномицеты, засоленные почвы, солеустойчивость, фосфатмобилизация, биопрепараты, устойчивое земледелие.*

Introduction

Agricultural lands in many regions of the world are subject to secondary salinization due to irrational irrigation and changes in hydrogeological conditions [1]. In Uzbekistan, the problem of saline soils is particularly relevant, since more than 50% of arable land is characterized by varying degrees of salinity [2]. This leads to a decrease in soil fertility and limited availability of macronutrients, in particular phosphorus. Actinomycetes are able to colonize the rhizosphere, act as endophytes or symbionts and positively affect plant growth by dissolving phosphates, producing phytohormones, reducing ethylene levels and protecting against phytopathogens. Phosphate-dissolving actinomycetes are of particular interest, but there is still less research in this area than on *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* [3]. Their ability to withstand salts and mobilize poorly soluble phosphates makes them promising agents in agricultural biotechnology

In this regard, the aim of this study was to investigate the salt tolerance and phosphate-mobilizing activity of actinomycetes isolated from saline agrocenoses of Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods

Sampling and isolation of actinomycetes. Soil samples were collected from a depth of 0–30 cm in saline agrocenoses of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Syrdarya region of Uzbekistan. Actinomycetes were isolated by serial dilution method on starch-ammonia agar (SAA) with the addition of NaCl (0.5%) and without NaCl. Strains were grown on an agar nutrient medium with the addition of NaCl at a concentration of 0.5 to 20%. Growth was assessed after 7–10 days of incubation at 28 °C.

Phosphate-mobilizing activity. To determine the ability to dissolve inorganic phosphates, Pikovskaya's medium with $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and an indicator was used. The initial color of the nutrient medium was dark purple. In the case of a change in the reaction of the medium to the acidic side under the influence of metabolites, the nutrient medium became discolored.

Results

The isolates were tested for salt stress tolerance at different NaCl concentrations (0.5% to 20%). The data for the 8 most salt-tolerant isolates are shown in Table 1, showing that not every isolate can tolerate high salt concentrations.

Table 1. Effect of different concentrations of NaCl salt on the growth of actinomycete isolates isolated from different soil-climatic conditions (7th day of the study)

Isolate No.	NaCl concentrations								
	Control	0,5%	1%	3%	5%	7%	10%	15%	20%
№1	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	-	-	-
№2	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	-	-	-
№3	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	-	-	-	-
№4	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	-	-	-
№5	+++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-	-
№6	+++	++	++	++	-	-	-	-	-
№7	+++	++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-
№13	+++	+++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-

Note: Qualitative assessment: - indicates the absence of growth; + indicates the presence of growth; additional + indicates the growth intensity exhibited by the isolates.

Thus, the growth of the isolates studied varied significantly, with some isolates being reduced and inhibited by salt. Almost all isolates grew well at 3% NaCl in the medium, but their growth varied significantly, isolate No.5 showed very poor growth (+). Isolates No.7 and 13

showed very poor growth (+) at 5% NaCl in the medium. Only three isolates, No.4, No.1 and No.2 grew at 7% NaCl in the medium, and these isolates demonstrated the highest salt tolerance.

Phosphate mobilizing activity was shown by 4 isolates, of which 2 had high activity (60–90%). Isolates No.7 and No.13 were the most active (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Phosphate mobilization properties of salt-tolerant actinomycete isolates
1- control; 2- isolate No.2; 3- isolate No. 5; 4- isolate No.7; 5- isolate No.13:

Discussion

The obtained results demonstrate high adaptability of actinomycetes to saline soil conditions. Their ability to tolerate NaCl concentrations up to 7% is consistent with other studies, and *Streptomyces* have been shown to be halotolerant to NaCl concentrations up to 900 mM and retain most of the PGPR traits under severe stress. Protects plants from salinization by acting systemically [4].

The phosphate-mobilizing activity of the isolates is of practical importance, since the availability of phosphorus in saline soils is usually limited due to the formation of poorly soluble calcium and magnesium salts. Particular attention is paid to representatives of the *Streptomyces* genus that have phosphorus-solubilizing activity. These microorganisms not only provide plants with available phosphorus, but also stimulate their growth due to the production of phytohormones, antibiotics, and other biologically active compounds [5]. The use of such microorganisms in the composition of biological preparations can increase the absorption of phosphorus by plants and promote crop yield growth.

Conclusion

As a result of the conducted research, 15 isolates of actinomycetes were isolated from saline soils of Uzbekistan. Eight of them showed resistance to salt stress in the range of 3-7% NaCl, and two isolates had phosphate-mobilizing activity. The most salt-tolerant isolates were No.4, No.1 and No.2, which withstood NaCl concentrations of up to 7%. Isolates No.13 and No.7 showed the ability to mobilize phosphates, which makes them promising candidates for the development of biofertilizers. The data obtained confirm the potential of actinomycetes in the creation of microbial inoculants adapted to the conditions of saline agrocenoses.

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